

Highlights

- Usual XRD and "in-situ" HTXRD of fired ceramic clay materials were compared.
- Reaction kinetics at high temperatures is different.
- Structural variations of high temperature phases can be observed by in situ HTXRD
- The transformation temperature can be more accurately determined by in-situ HTXRD.

1 **Mineralogical evolution of ceramic clays during heating according to the “in situ”**
2 **high temperature X-ray diffraction (HTXRD) study**

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9

10 **ABSTRACT**

11 The ceramic properties of clay materials heated at high temperature are largely
12 dependent on the mineral reactions, which usually are followed by XRD analysis on
13 pressed pieces that are heated at different temperatures. Nevertheless, the use of “in-situ”
14 high temperature X-ray diffraction (HTXRD) to follow the evolution of the crystalline
15 phases under controlled temperature provides more precision. In this paper, the
16 mineralogical changes produced during firing (RT-1000°C) of two clay materials of very
17 different mineralogical composition, frequently used in the manufacture of bricks in the
18 SE Spain, have been studied by XRD classical procedure and with HTXRD, and the
19 results obtained were compared. Although the phases identified by both X-ray analyses
20 were the same, temperatures for the mineralogical reactions are different, probably due
21 to the different run speed of the two experiments. The patterns obtained by XRD were at
22 a higher speed than those by HTXRD, and probably the equilibrium was not achieved for
23 the most reactions.

24 In addition, there are some difficulties for a good identification of high-temperature
25 phases using “in-situ” HTXRD analysis due to the expansion of the mineral structure

26 parameters. Consequently, mineral reflections do not match with those found in the
27 database JPCD, neither the position nor intensities of some stable phases at high
28 temperature. For the optimization of the interpretation of the HTXRD patterns, and to
29 facilitate the kinetic of the new phases, it is necessary to work at a high integration time
30 per step and a slow heating rate.

31 The HTXRD investigations of ceramic materials can save time respect to XRD study
32 of test-pieces heated at different temperatures, and lead immediate information of the
33 transformation occurring on heating, which can be useful to improve the most suitable
34 firing temperature in the industry.

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36 **1. Introduction and objectives**

37 The mineral changes produced during heating on ceramic materials are usually
38 followed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) on test pieces prepared on laboratory and heated at
39 appropriate temperatures (Castellanos et al., 2012; Cultrone et al., 2001; González-García
40 et al., 1990; González et al., 1985; Jordán et al., 2009, 1999; Santana et al., 2012; Serra
41 et al., 2013; Trindade et al., 2010, 2009). Nevertheless, this technique does not enable to
42 follow the continuous mineral evolution. In addition, many test pieces are needed to
43 obtain XRD patterns at short temperature intervals, which is very tedious and slow.

44 In the last years, the analysis by high temperature X-ray diffraction technique
45 (HTXRD) has been used to follow the continuous evaluation of crystalline phases during
46 a controlled temperature ramp. This method avoids errors induced by the movement of
47 the samples, providing more truthful information and saving experimental time (Bohor,
48 1963; Mazzucato et al., 1999; Wahl et al., 1961; Wang et al., 2017). In addition, the new
49 software available with adjustment of profiles, intensities, etc. allows to assess the

50 structural changes of each phase (parameters variations, polymorphic changes,
51 destruction and crystallization of new phases).

52 The aim of this contribution is to compare the results obtained by HTXRD with those
53 deduced from the classical approach by XRD of two raw clay ceramic materials during
54 heating at high temperature in order to evaluate the possible advantage of the first
55 technique.

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57 **2. Materials and Methods**

58 The two clays studied are commonly used in ceramic industries of Bailén (SE Spain).
59 Locally, they are called “red loam” (RARJ) and “black loam” (BANG) and they were
60 chosen because of their very different mineralogical composition. According to González
61 et al., (2006, 1985), RARJ contains illite, as the main clay mineral, and it is poor in
62 carbonates, while BANG contains illite and smectites and is richer in carbonates.

63 The XRD was carried out on pressed disks that were crushed, sieved at $<50\mu\text{m}$ and
64 measured using a powder diffractometer (Bruker D8I Advance with LYNXEYE
65 detector), working at standards conditions (Cu $k\alpha$ radiation 1.54056\AA , 40kV and 30 mA,
66 $3-70^\circ 2\theta$, step size 0.015° and time per step 0.1 s with divergence slit 0.5°). The disks
67 were fired in an electric kiln at 500, 700, 800, 900 and 1000°C with a rate of $5^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$
68 and they were kept at maximum temperature for 2 h.

69 The “in-situ” HTXRD analysis was carried out using a powder diffractometer (Bruker
70 DISCOVER D8) equipped with a chamber (MTC-FURNACE) with corundum sample
71 holder and a fast response/high sensibility detector (Bruker, LYNXEYE-XE).

72 In order to choose the most appropriate working conditions, several XRD patterns
73 were obtained at different step size, time per step and heating rate (Figure 1). At high
74 heating rates, the absorption of radiation by the chamber was very strong and the

75 resolution of the patterns was very low. Therefore, the selected working conditions were
76 Cu $k\alpha$ radiation 1.54056Å, 40Kv and 40 mA, 3-70°2 θ , with a step size 0.01°, time per
77 step 1 s, temperatures variables from RT up to 1000°C, and rate of 2°C·min⁻¹. The
78 conditions lead to more accurate HTXRD patterns than those obtained by XRD.

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86 Fig. 1. HTXRD patterns of sample RARJ obtained at 500°C at different experimental
87 conditions. 1: step size 0.01° and time per step 1 s; 2: step size 0.02° and time per step
88 0.2 s.

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90 Phase identification of samples was accomplished using EVA v. 16.0.0.0 software.
91 The clay mineralogy of the raw materials was determined on oriented aggregates of the
92 <2 μ m fraction, after air-drying, ethylene-glycol solvation and heating to 550°C. A
93 quantitative mineralogical approach (semi-quantitative mineralogical analysis) was
94 achieved measuring the diagnostic peak areas, considering the full width and half
95 maximum (FWHM), and corrected by empirical factors according to Galán and Martín
96 Vivaldi, (1973), Martín-Pozas et al., (1971) and Schultz, (1964). The total proportion of
97 clay minerals in each sample was first determined by considering the area of the reflection
98 at 4.48 Å in the random powder patterns. The percentages of the different clay minerals

99 were then obtained from the areas of the diagnostic basal reflection of the species in the
100 glycolated clay fraction.

101 As in general the lattice of minerals are changing with the increasing temperature, in
102 some selected phases the lattice parameters were calculated by Le Bail algorithms using
103 Topas 5 software.

104 The chemical analysis of the raw materials was performed by sequential spectrometer
105 of X-ray fluorescence (XRF) Panalytical mod. AXIOS with Rh tube. The measurements
106 were performed in glass bead (sample/flux dilution ratio was 10/90). The detection limit
107 was averaged on ten analyses of flux (lithium borate), plus three times the typical
108 deviation and the quantification limit plus ten times the typical deviation.

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110 3. Results and Discussion

111 The “red loam” RARJ is composed of quartz, illite, dolomite and hematite, with traces
112 of kaolinite, calcite, K-feldspars and anatase (Table 1). The “black loam” BANG is richer
113 in carbonates (calcite 18% and dolomite 21%), with quartz, illite and smectite, and some
114 gypsum, anatase and pyrite. The chemical composition (Table 2) reasonably agrees with
115 the mineralogy.

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117 Table 1. Mineralogical composition of raw samples (%). Qz: quartz, I: illite, Cal: calcite,
118 Dol: dolomite, K-Fsp: K-feldspars, Ab: albite, Hem: hematite, Py: pyrite, Gp: gypsum,
119 Ant: anatase, Sm: smectites, Kaol: kaolinite. tr: trace (<5%).

Sample	Qz	I	Cal	Dol	K-Fsp	Ab	Hem	Py	Gp	Ant	Sm	Kaol
RARJ	34	45	tr	7	tr	--	7	--	--	tr	--	tr
BANG	31	14	18	21	tr	tr	--	tr	tr	tr	7	tr

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121 Table 2. Chemical composition of raw samples (wt %). LoQ: below quantification limit.

122 LOI: Lost on ignition.

Sample	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MnO	MgO	CaO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	TiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	LOI	TOTAL
RARJ	56.65	17.72	7.73	0.09	2.54	1.44	0.22	5.14	0.85	0.15	LoQ	5.79	98.36
BANG	48.92	8.76	3.79	LoQ	3.60	12.77	0.36	2.36	0.59	0.09	2.44	17.29	101.01
LoD	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.22		
LoQ	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.10	0.02	0.23		

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124 The mineralogical evolution obtained by HTXRD and that deduced from the classical
 125 approach by XRD is shown in Figure 2. The firing behavior of no-calcareous and
 126 calcareous sample is considerably different because of the initial mineralogical
 127 composition. Moreover, the presence of calcite, dolomite or both can influence the
 128 formation of different minerals at high temperatures (Trindade et al., 2010).

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142 Fig. 2. Comparison between the mineral phases found with the two procedures and their
 143 evolution with the temperature (dot lines are doubtful interpretation).

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145 Overall data of XRD and HTXRD are quite similar, although in HTXRD the mineral
146 transformation temperatures were more accurate and more precise, because they were
147 performed with greater sensitivity.

148 • Dolomite destroyed at 700°C - 740°C (in the heated disk by XRD, dolomite does
149 not appear at 700°C), which was significantly higher than that referred by Criado
150 and González-García (1976) (650°C) and lesser than that referred by Trindade et
151 al., (2010) (800-900°C). Gunasekaran and Anbalagan (2007) reported that
152 dolomite disappears at 750°C and Trindade et al., (2009) cited the beginning of
153 its destruction at 600°C. Dolomite decomposition was not observed in a two-step
154 process with a previous transformation in calcite as suggested by several authors
155 (Gunasekaran and Anbalagan, 2007; Rat'ko et al., 2011; Webb and Kruger, 1970).
156 On the contrary, the intensity of calcite reflection at 3.03Å was gradually
157 decreasing up to 840°C, according to Serra et al., (2013).

158 • Calcite disappeared at 680°C in sample RARJ, where it was present as a minor
159 component. However, it remained up to 840°C in sample BANG (by XRD calcite
160 did not appear at 800°C).

161 • The formation of lime, periclase, diopside, and gehlenite were mainly related to
162 the destruction of dolomite and calcite.

163 • Lime only was observed in sample BANG, starting at around 700°C and
164 remaining up to 1000°C. Probably the small amount of calcite in RARJ did not
165 result detectable lime.

166 • Periclase, which essentially forms from the destruction of dolomite, occurred at
167 820°C in RARJ (800°C by XRD). However, it appeared at 700°C in BANG
168 (detected both by XRD and HTXRD) probably due to the destruction of smectites

169 too. In both samples, periclase was not totally destroyed at higher temperatures
170 and it remained up to 1000°C coexisting with diopside.

171 • The presence of diopside is doubtful. It occurs in the range 840-900°C in RARJ,
172 while, in BANG, it appears at 880°C and remains up to 1000°C, according to
173 results of Peters and Iberg, (1978).

174 • The occurrence of gehlenite was highly dependent on the Ca content, as the case
175 of lime. In sample RARJ, which is poor in Ca, it was detected at very small
176 concentrations at 800°C by XRD, but it did not appear up to 950°C by HTXRD.
177 In sample BANG, it was detected by both techniques at 900°C. These results are
178 in agreement with Peters and Iberg (1978).

179 • Illite remains up to 1000°C, but above 900°C probably starts its destruction,
180 because the diffraction intensities are lower.

181 • Anatase continues clearly up to 1000°C in RARJ, in spite of the transformation to
182 rutile should theoretically occur at around 600°C (Hanaor and Sorrell, 2011). In
183 BANG this result was not possible to be observed because the overlapping with
184 anhydrite.

185 • In spite of many authors cite the presence of wollastonite, larnite, and other high
186 temperature Ca-phases with the heating of carbonated materials similar to BANG
187 (El Ouahabi et al., 2015; González-García et al., 1990; Jordán et al., 2009, 1999,
188 Trindade et al., 2010, 2009), those phases were not found in this study. As the d-
189 values of the reflections of diopside and wollastonite are very close (2.98-2.99Å,
190 respectively) other reflections were sought to confirm the absence of that last
191 phase. The same occurred with the d-values of gehlenite and lime (2.40Å and
192 2.41Å, respectively), but in this case the presence of other reflections confirmed
193 the occurrence of both minerals at high temperature. Therefore, if the diagram

194 does not have enough quality, some phases that are in small quantity or not well
195 ordered can be hidden in the background.

196 In the same way, the presence of a spinel was not detected, which according to
197 Jordán et al. (2009) and González-García et al. (1990) should be formed in
198 samples rich in illite and quartz as RARJ. This could be because the reflection at
199 2.44Å of spinel coincides with others of quartz and illite and because spinel starts
200 to form at higher temperatures (1100°C according to Trindade et al., 2009).

201 • Gypsum, only present in BANG, transformed to basanite over 50°C and then to
202 anhydrite (380°C), which was observed up to 1000°C.

203 The HTXRD patterns interpretation is generally more difficult because the lattice
204 parameters of minerals are changing with the increasing temperature (Fig. 3).
205 Consequently, this produces a significant variation in the d-spacing values that sometimes
206 causes a great difficulty in the interpretation of the patterns (Fig. 4 and Fig. 5). The same
207 must occur when test pieces were heated to be analyzed by XRD, but after cooling, most
208 mineral structural parameters came back to the original ones, or at least to close position.
209 Moreover, many diffraction effects at high temperature are usually overlapped, as it is the
210 case for gehlenite, diopside, or lime. However, as quartz transformation is reversible after
211 cooling, the position of quartz reflection can be used as reference (Fig. 6).

212 In general, it is to be noted that both diffraction patterns, obtained by the two
213 techniques, cannot be directly compared because the running conditions are very different
214 and, consequently, the transformation/destruction kinetic of the phases never may occurs
215 at the same temperatures.

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XRD

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229 Fig. 3. Variation of lattice volume in illite, quartz and hematite with temperature.

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243 Fig. 4. Variations of the d-spacing values of the main reflection corresponding to illite,
 244 quartz, calcite and dolomite after heating in situ HTXRD.

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— Illite Dehydroxilation
 — Quartz α → β (573°C)

258 Fig. 5. Isolines of HTXRD patterns of the samples studied. Some strong reflections of
 259 illite (I), quartz (Qz), calcite (Cal), dolomite (Do), anatase (Ant), hematite (Hem),
 260 gypsum (Gp), basanite (Bas), K-feldspars (K-Fsp), albite (Ab), diopside (Di), lime (L)
 261 and gehlenite (Gh) are marked, and the transformation quartz α-β and dehydroxilation of
 262 illite are clearly showed with two horizontal bands.

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281 Fig. 6. XRD patterns of sample RARJ showing intensities variations of reflections

282 recorded after heating and the displacements due to dilatation/shrinkage for illite and

283 hematite parameters (ellipses), which were maintained after cooling. This did not occur

284 for quartz (see zoom) because of its reversibility.

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286 4. Conclusion

287 The HTXRD investigations of ceramic materials can save time respect to the XRD

288 study of test-pieces heated at different temperatures, and lead immediate truthful

289 information about the transformations occurring on heating. If the experiments are carried

290 out with sufficient sensitivity, very accuracy patterns can be obtained in which the

291 structural variations of the present phases can be studied. This information can be useful

292 to improve the most suitable firing temperature in the industry.

293 The temperature ramp and the number of patterns obtained are critical to properly set
294 the phase transitions.

295 The main inconvenient for the using of the “in-situ” HTXRD analysis is the difficulty
296 found in the interpretation, because, due to the dilatation of lattice parameters, mineral
297 reflections do not match with those found in the data base JPCD, neither the position nor
298 intensities of some stable phases at high temperature.

299 For the optimization of the HTXRD diagrams and to facilitate the transition
300 temperatures of new phases, it is necessary to establish a high integration time per step
301 and a slow heating rate. In order to obtain optimal results, the conditions of data collection
302 should be determined prior to the analysis. The main factors to determine are the
303 wavelength, the collimation of the beam, the angular range and angular distance between
304 the steps and counting time. The choice of appropriate values for the count time (which
305 defines the intensity) and for angular interval of step (which in a given interval determines
306 the number of steps) depends on the experimental conditions and characteristics of the
307 studied material.

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313

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